

Design and implementation of DC meter for PV plants

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Abstract. Due to the growth of photovoltaic plants both in Spain and the rest of the world, it causes a technological development in the normal operation of these plants. In this sense, the authors have developed a DC meter for use in PV plants based on current regulations. The hardware implementation of the meter is based on sensors that allow the measurement of electrical variables such as voltage, current and power. And the software design allows the different electrical variables to be measured in real time. The calibration process of the equipment is carried out according to IEC standards. Furthermore, the measurement and processing of the data obtained is carried out by means of a microcontroller.

Keywords: Photovoltaic, Data acquisition; IEC standards; low-cost; open source; Smart Direct Current in Real-Time

1 Introduction

The consumption of electricity is increasing every year and this leads to an increase in new photovoltaic (PV) plants and their integration into the electricity grids. This makes the electricity system more and more reliable and sustainable. Therefore, PV plants must perform optimally during their operation time.

The evaluation of PV requires the measurement of electrical variables in small time intervals. This causes problems due to the large amount of data and equipment that must be reliable and accurate. In the case of large-scale plants, this approach is technically and economically challenging, as it requires extending measurements down to the module level across a very large field [1]. The need for sensors to measure variables in each module, as well as the cost of the integrated monitoring system, increases proportionally with the size of the PV plant [2,3]. The current standard for PV plant monitoring based on UNE-EN IEC 61724-1 [4] entitled PV system performance. Part 1: Monitoring. The standard indicates the recording of the electrical variables defined in point 11 of this standard.

Furthermore, data management requires a large storage space and post-processing, it is complex especially in large plants. In addition, communication problems may arise from each individual unit to the central unit.

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The monitoring equipment must include the electrical variables that allow the plant operation to be evaluated in real time. From the electrical point of view, direct current (DC), voltage and power must be measured [2].

The hardware design must distinguish several monitoring levels (i) plant level; (ii) inverter level; (iii) DC module string grouping; (iv) DC PV module string; (v) DC PV module.

The PV plant measurement equipment on the DC side of the inverter shall be equipped with voltage and current sensors, which allow power and energy assessment. The equipment for PV module strings and conjunction of these strings will contain voltage and current (DC) sensors. Finally, module level equipment will implement DC voltage and current sensors.

Some authors have designed plant (AC) measurement equipment with installed voltage, current and frequency sensors, which allow to obtain RMS, harmonics, power and energy values [12,13,14]. The software design methodology must integrate the measurement [15] and sending of data at a minimum rate of electrical variables [11].

The performance evaluation will be based on current plant operating data and reference values. To manage the information obtained and operate accordingly, a server is designed in the plant that brings together all the data generated, so that it is available for monitoring the plant. Additionally, the data will be uploaded to the cloud at the recording interval and will be accessible for external consultation.

2 Design FV

2.1. Hardware

2.1.1. Microcontroller

The DC measurement device designed and developed in this article requires a powerful and fast microcontroller, as measurements need to be taken at very small-time intervals. Another important factor is memory, since a large number of voltage and current measurements must be made and stored. Therefore, in addition to having a large memory capacity, it is essential that the microcontroller can quickly access the stored data to perform the necessary calculations.

An open development platform is used that can accommodate other peripherals that complement the functions of the microcontroller. Examples could be storage on a memory card or a real-time clock that provides the date and time of each measurement. The Arduino family is therefore particularly interesting to use. They are low-cost devices for this type of application. Finally, it is important that the size of the microcontroller is small.

An added feature of Teensy 4.1 [16] is that it includes a device for microSD cards up to 32 GB, which does not require additional storage hardware, and because it is included on the board, it has a higher speed. In terms of size, the smallest model is the Teensy 4.1. Therefore, taking into account the microprocessor, available RAM, size, price and additional options, the Teensy 4.1 microcontroller has been chosen for the DC measurement.

2.1.2. Voltage measurement circuit

The first stage of the signal conditioning circuit for the voltage circuit consists of five 1000 kΩ, 1/4 W resistors in series, which form a voltage divider together with another 10 kΩ resistor, the value of which has been determined according to the specifications in the component datasheet. The voltage divider is designed to cause a voltage drop of 2 V across the 10 kΩ resistor when the input voltage is 1000 V.

The next component is a high-precision optically isolated voltage sensor, specifically the ACPL-C87A [17] from Broad-com. Its function is to provide optical isolation to electrically separate the input and output signals, providing safety and protection against electrical interference. This feature also has a positive influence on the reliability of the measurement, since the voltage to be measured is referenced to the negative pole, whose voltage may not be zero, while the amplifier output signal is referenced to an isolated ground which it shares with the other components of the circuit.

Fig. 1. Signal conditioning for the voltage measurement circuit

The ACPL-C87A has a nominal input range of 0 to 2 V with a very high input impedance ($R_{in} = 1 \text{ G}\Omega$), in the case where $(R1+R2+R3+R4+R5) \gg R2$, the component error can be estimated as:

$$e(\%) = \frac{R2}{R_{in}} \cdot 100 = \frac{10 \cdot 10^3}{1 \cdot 10^9} \cdot 100 = 0.001\% \tag{1}$$

Fig. 2. ACPL-C87A internal circuit scheme

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To power this component, two 5 V supplies are required, one of which is isolated and whose neutral is connected as a reference to the input signal GND1, while the other is connected with respect to the output signal ground GND2.

The next component is an operational amplifier OP07CPZ [18] acting as a subtractor, since the input voltage to the ACLP is equivalent to the voltage difference between Vout+ and Vout- at the output of the component.

Fig. 3. LTC6911-2 amplifier pins scheme

Once the signal has been subtracted, it is amplified using the LTC6911-2 [19], a programmable gain amplifier, which allows the voltage signal to be adjusted to approximate the full scale of the ADC. In this way, the relative accuracy of the measurement can be increased for the same resolution. The amplifier has two channels A and B, which are capable of providing up to 5 V each, although in this case only channel A has been used, as the maximum output voltage will be 3.3 V (input voltage to the Teensy).

The component is dual-powered at ± 5 V, and its digital pins G0, G1 and G2 are activated by the Teensy 4.1, being a logic one when they take the 5 V value. However, the microcontroller's digital pins provide a 3.3 V output when they are on, so a voltage converter is needed to boost this voltage to the 5 V required by the LTC6911-2 to make the gain adjustment.

Next, because passing through the LTC6911-2 inverts the signal to be measured, an operational amplifier acts as an inverter. Finally, to reduce noise, a first-order RC low-pass filter is placed at the end of the circuit.

2.1.3. Current measurement circuit

The HSTS016L sensor [20], which provides a voltage signal that increases proportionally with the current passing through the conductor, is used for current measurements. One of its main characteristics is that it is non-invasive, due to its split core, that allows the conductor to be wrapped around it without requiring any modifications to the circuit being measured. It has a measuring range from -30 A to 30 A, with an output value of 2.5 V when there is no current flowing through the conductor; this voltage is the reference voltage and remains constant at the sensor's Vref output. Since the objectives do not include measuring negative current, the conditioning circuit has been designed so that a 0 V output corresponds to 0 A in the conductor. For this reason, the reference signal Vref has been subtracted from the Vout clamp's output signal using an operational amplifier configured as a subtractor. The sensor is powered by 5 V.

The next part of the circuit is the same as the voltage circuit explained above: the signal is amplified by the LTC6911-2, inverted, and filtered before reaching the analogue pin of the microcontroller.

Fig. 4. Signal conditioning for the current measurement circuit

2.1.4. Power supply circuit

Once the characteristics of the meter, the communications, and the components that are part of the voltage and current modules have been defined, it becomes possible to determine and calculate the voltages and power required from the sources that make up the equipment's power supply module.

The power supply circuit includes an AC-DC source (PSK-15D-9) [21] that converts the mains voltage into a continuous 9V signal, from which the voltages required by the components of the designed circuits are derived. This source has an efficiency of 84% and a power rating of 15 W, which exceeds the demand of the equipment. The circuit is equipped with a 3.15 A fuse and a 350 V varistor to protect it from over-voltage. Additionally, two capacitors are mounted at the source's output: a 1 μF ceramic capacitor with 50V insulation and a 100 μF electrolytic capacitor with at least 25V insulation, to reduce output voltage ripple. The characteristics required for both capacitors are specified in the component's datasheet.

A DC-DC converter was used for the isolated 5 V supply needed to power the isolation amplifier of the voltage circuit, as it provides an independent ground and 5 V signal at its input, with 1 W of power. The selected component is the IHA0109S05 [22], to which a 470 μF capacitor has been added at its input, as specified in its datasheet.

The 5 V supply is provided by an LDO LD1085V50 [23] regulator, with 10 μF electrolytic capacitors installed at both the input and output to ensure stability. The regulator can deliver up to 7.5 W of power.

Finally, for the -5 V supply, an isolated TEC 2-0911 DC-DC converter [24] was used, which is supplied with 9 V at the input and provides a 5 V output, whose polarity can be reversed due to its isolation from the main source. In this case, the positive output is connected to ground, and the negative output is connected to the -5 V supply of the components. It is capable of delivering up to 5.4 W of power with an efficiency of 81%.

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The Table 1 shows the power consumption of the elements that make up the string-level electricity meter, while Table 2 presents the output power and efficiency of the selected sources.

Fig. 5. Power supply circuit

Table 1. Maximum power demanded by the equipment.

Amount	Component	Voltage			
		5 V	-5 V	5 V isolated	3,3 V
1	Voltage measurement circuit	186.5 mW	121.5 mW	60 mW	5 mW
3	Current measurement circuit	129.6 mW	64.6 mW		5 mW
1	Teensy 4.1	500 mW			
1	LoRa	25 mW			
1	ESP32 S2 Mini	2500 mW			
Total		3600.3 mW	315.3 mW	60 mW	20 mW

Table 2. Efficiency and output power of each source.

Component	Maximum output power (mW)	Efficiency (%)	Real power consumption (mW)
LD1085V50 (5 V)	7,500 mW	55.55	6481.19 mW
TEC 2-0911 (-5 V)	2,000 mW	81	389.26 mW
IHA0109S05 (5 V iso)	1,000 mW	77	77.92 mW

PSK-15D-9-DIN (9 V)	15,000 mW	84	8271.7 mW
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2.2. Software design

2.2.1. Main program

The program running on the Teensy 4.1 microcontroller is responsible for taking measurements of the electrical parameters. The program can be divided into the following routines:

- Start-up routine: The program starts with the configuration of analogue (measurement) and digital (control) pins with their respective ADCs, it also defines the variables and initialises the SD reader, as well as any hardware necessary for the operation of the equipment.
- Measurement routine: The voltage and current values of each string are read synchronously. It compares the received signal with the maximum input voltage values of the analogue pin, and if the threshold is exceeded, the LTC gain is adjusted downwards to protect the meter. The gain is then progressively increased until the optimum accuracy for the detected voltage and current level is reached. Finally, the constant assigned to the gain set in each case is applied.
- Data sending routine: The data sending routine creates a CSV file (if it does not already exist) to store the measured data in the SD card's memory. Finally, it waits 500 ms before returning to the start of the measurement routine.

Fig. 6. Flowchart of the microcontroller Teensy 4.1 code

3 Results

In the results section, different tests have been carried out at both the theoretical and experimental levels. Firstly, the voltage and current circuits have been calibrated, which makes it possible to analyse the tendency of the sensors for different voltage and current levels of the circuits designed. Subsequently, ramp tests were carried out to study the operation of the circuits.

3.1. Calibration of Measurement Circuits.

3.1.1. Voltage circuit

To perform the calibration of the voltage circuit, first of all, theoretical calculations of the calibration constants corresponding to each gain of the circuit were carried out. In this way, the optimum measured voltage level at which the gain change is to be made can be found. Then, using the PQ-Box 300 [25] network analyser as a reference, the circuit calibration was performed, yielding the equation that relates the number of bits read to the voltage in the circuit for the different ranges in which each gain operates.

The experimental calibration test was conducted for a DC voltage of up to 560 V, due to the limitations of the standard equipment. However, given the linear behaviour of the equipment, the calibration performed will allow accurate measurements up to 830 V.

Fig. 7. Theoretical calibration constants for the voltage metering circuit

Figure 7 shows the theoretical calibration constants up to 1000 V values. And figure 8 shows the experimental calibration constants up to values of 830 V.

As we can see, the slope obtained in the theoretical calculations and in the experimental test is very similar; however, differences can be observed in some decimals and in the offset, which was unknown when carrying out the theoretical calculations.

Fig. 8. Experimental calibration constants for the voltage metering circuit

3.1.2. Current circuit.

In the case of the current circuit, we proceeded in a similar way to the voltage circuit, in this case using the Siglent CP4050 clamp ammeter [26], as the analyser previously used does not have sensors capable of measuring direct current. In this case, the experimental calibration test was carried out up to a continuous current of 10.5 A, due to the 11 A limitation of the equipment acting as a load. As it is a linear sensor, it is able to take current measurements accurately up to 18.5A.

Figure 9 shows the theoretical calibration constants up to a value of 30 A.

Fig. 9. Theoretical calibration constants for the current metering circuit

Figure 10 shows the experimental calibration constants up to a value of 18.5A.

Fig. 10. Experimental calibration constants for the current metering circuit

As with the voltage circuit, the calibration constants obtained vary very little from the theoretical values. Once again, the experimental data show an offset voltage specific

to the conditioning circuit which was not taken into account in the theoretical calculations.

3.2. Performance tests

3.2.1. Voltage circuit

In order to check the measurement accuracy of the designed voltage circuit, a voltage slope test was carried out, which consisted of taking measurements of a signal that increases progressively from 0 to 560 V. The test was carried out for the standard unit and the designed unit simultaneously, and the data obtained were plotted together in Fig. 11. The test was carried out simultaneously for the standard unit and the designed unit, and the data obtained were plotted together in the graph in Fig. 11.

In Fig. 11, several points outside the expected values can be seen, these are located at the voltages at which the circuit performs the gain change. These points appear because the software is designed to protect the circuit in case of overvoltage, therefore, when the input voltage to the microcontroller exceeds 3.25 V the gain is set to 1, using its respective constant, and increases progressively until it reaches the most appropriate value. These points with abnormal values can be removed from the registers by the software, so they are not a problem.

Fig. 11. Increasing voltage test for the voltage metering circuit

3.2.2. Current circuit

For the current circuit, we have proceeded in a similar way to the previous section, taking measurements with the designed circuit, applying an increasing current from 0 to 10.5 A, and then decreasing from the maximum value to zero with the same slope.

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Again, some values outside the expected range can be seen, as in the voltage circuit, these values indicate the change in gain and can be eliminated by software.

In this case, the number of samples taken in the ramp is significantly small, this is due to the fact that the source with which the test was carried out is not capable of generating a current ramp with a lower slope.

Fig. 12. Increasing current test for the voltage metering circuit

4. Conclusions

In this research, the authors develop and implement a low-cost prototype PV meter for measuring photovoltaic electrical installations in domestic and industrial environments. The core of the prototype is the Teensy 4.1 microcontroller, compatible with the open-source Arduino platform.

The advantages are many. These include obtaining the basic variables, current and voltage in accordance with the IEC 61724-1 standard. To perform the stationary analysis, measurements every 500 ms are used, which conforms to the specific standard. The sampling and calculation of the measured signal is possible due to the processing capacity of the microprocessor, which is another of the advantages of great interest offered by the equipment for use in Smart grids.

To validate the operation of the prototype and check that it is valid for use in Smart grids, it has been validated in a network emulator together with an electronic load that allows voltage and current ramps to be simulated with the desired slope and characteristics.

In addition, the prototype design includes readily available hardware and open-source software. This means that it is freely accessible to researchers and general users for their own design in a non-intrusive way.

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